

MethodsNET 2025

2nd MethodsNET Conference

The global hub for research methods innovations, excellence and smart use

<https://methodsnet.org/conference/2nd-methodsnet-conference/>

Proceedings of the Conference

*Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium
10 - 12 September, 2025*

The MethodsNET organizers gratefully acknowledge the support from the following sponsors.

Co-hosted by:

Sponsors:

Introduction

The 2nd MethodsNET conference is a unique global event that brings together research methods experts (developers, innovators, teachers), along with research methods users and learners at different stages of their careers. The event covers the full spectrum of methodologies, methods, and techniques across the ‘human sciences’, i.e., the study of the social, behavioral, biological, cultural, and philosophical dimensions of human life.

The Conference is designed to be a platform for sharing work-in-progress, cutting-edge developments and innovations, receiving expert feedback and advice, learning about recently developed toolboxes, and networking. It is a unique global networking arena around research methods.

Thanks to the diverse session formats, the Conference aims to meet the diverse needs of scholars and practitioners. It offers a platform for dialogue and exchange across methodologies and disciplines, as we believe that there is especially a lot to learn among researchers from diverse disciplines that are developing and/or using similar research methods. It is also a great occasion for the members of the recently launched digital *MethodsNET Communities* to gather in person and brainstorm around joint initiatives and projects.

The Conference’s overall agenda is both about reflecting together (experts/developers and users) on emerging methodological topics and innovations, AND about enabling the smart (sharp and robust) exploitation of existing research methods by method users, in particular by providing them with diverse types of training sessions and with feedback on their work-in-progress.

Organizing Committee

Advisory Committee

Conference Co-chairs

Ulrike Lühe, University of British Columbia

Ulrike Lühe is a Postdoctoral Fellow at the School of Public Policy and Global Affairs and the iSchool at the University of British Columbia. Her work focuses on the international politics of knowledge production, documentation and archiving in conflict and post-conflict settings, transitional justice, and research methods in International Relations. Before joining UBC, she completed her PhD at the University of Basel, Switzerland and worked at swisspeace. Ulrike's work has been published in *International Affairs*, the *International Journal of Transitional Justice*, the *International Journal of Human Rights* and others.

M. Taimoor Khan, GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences

M. Taimoor Khan is a senior researcher in the Knowledge Technologies for Social Sciences department at GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences. With a background in computer science, his research focuses on applied machine learning, natural language processing, dynamically adapting models and computational reproducibility. He has also led the development of big data infrastructure and NLP tools for low resourced languages. At GESIS, he is part of the Methods Hub project aiming to lower the technical barriers in reusing reproducible large computational models. He has contributed to EU project and has published in top-tier computer

science venues.

Benoît Rihoux, MethodsNET EB

Benoît Rihoux is full professor in comparative politics at the University of Louvain (UCLouvain), Belgium. He is an international leader in the field of comparative methods and designs, in particular around Configurational Comparative Methods (CCMs) and Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA). He is the initiator of the COMPASSS global network in the field of CCM and has produced multiple reference publications on QCA, including the most cited textbook on the topic (Rihoux and Ragin 2009). He also publishes on mixed- and multimethod designs and is involved in diverse disciplinary, interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary comparative and cross-case projects involving QCA and mixed method designs; in these projects, he has tackled very different types of cases: micro-

level, meso-level and macro-level, across social sciences and health. He has taught QCA, comparative research designs, research design and soft skills for researchers at numerous venues across the globe. He was joint initiator and joint Academic Convenor of the ECPR Methods School from 2006 to 2021 and is joint initiator and current Chair of MethodsNET, as well as joint Academic Coordinator of the Summer School in Social Research Methods (3SRM).

Committee Member

Clemence Bouchat, KU Leuven

Clemence is currently working as a doctoral researcher at KU Leuven. She is affiliated with the Public Governance Institute. Her research interests include crisis governance, evidence-informed policymaking, political networks and narratives.

Web Chair

Anna Foley Executive Administrator

Proceedings Committee Chair

M. Taimoor Khan, GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences

Best Paper Awards Candidates

(in no specific order)

- Sho Niikawa and Airo Hino, *"Pitfalls of relying on standard interaction model, authors"*
- Eva Zavadilová, *"Triangulating Perspectives"*
- Charlotte Parion, *"Towards a Relational Type of Systematicity in Scoping Reviews"*
- Jessy Hendriks, Barbara Vis, and Koen Damhuis, *"Under Which Conditions Do Politicians Bash and Praise Public Organizations? A Mixed-Methods Analysis of Politicians' Strategic Framing on X (Twitter)"*
- Anna Broka, *"Youth Welfare Regimes and Political Culture in the European Union (EU)"*
- Laura Camfield, *"Reimagining the Methodological Horizon"*
- Sophie Prantil, *"Preserving the Working-Class Vote"*
- Joost de Moor, *"Climate system temporalities and strategic dilemmas in climate activism"*
- Hedye Tayebi-Jazayeri, *"The View from Somewhere"*

1st Keynote Talk: Ensuring Social Scientific Data Quality and Reproducibility in the Big Data/AI Era: Challenges and Pathways by Prof. Stefan Dietze

Abstract:

Throughout the last decades, the social sciences have increasingly adopted novel forms of research data, e.g. data mined from the web and social media platforms. This together with the recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI) and related areas, e.g. natural language processing (NLP), led to a much more widespread adoption of diverse computational methods, including techniques from machine learning and, most prominently, large language models. However, increasingly complex computational methods lead to new challenges with respect to transparency, reproducibility and overall quality of social science research and data, further elevating an already widely recognised reproducibility crisis. This talk will, on the one hand, introduce challenges posed by the use of AI-based methods in social science research. On the other hand, it will show pathways to address such problems. Examples are works geared towards sharing computational (AI) methods in the social sciences in a reproducible and citable way, for understanding and tracing adoption of and relations between methods and datasets at large scale, e.g. in social science research in general (e.g. by mining scientific publications) or novel ways for providing access to sensitive research data in the social sciences (e.g. social media data) to facilitate reproducible research without violating ethical or legal constraints or principles.

Stefan Dietze is full professor for Data & Knowledge Engineering at Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf (HHU), and scientific director of the department Knowledge Technologies for the Social Sciences (KTS) at GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences in Cologne (Germany). He is also deputy director at the Heine Center for Artificial Intelligence & Data Science (HeiCAD) at HHU and affiliated with the L3S Research Center (Hannover, Germany) and the Düsseldorf Institute for Internet & Democracy (DIID). His research is at the intersection of natural language processing, information retrieval and machine learning, specifically aimed at developing AI-based methods for mining and understanding large volumes of data, such as data mined from the Web and social media platforms, and their application in the social sciences. Stefan has obtained

substantial research funding as PI and Co-PI at national and international level and he frequently publishes at top tier conferences such as EMNLP, NAACL, The WebConf, SIGIR or Web Science and in high impact journals, where he also serves as editorial board and program committee member.

2nd Keynote Talk: The Tangible Truth: Quality Assessment beyond the Gold Standard into the Age of New Materialism by Prof. Karin Hannes

Abstract:

Prof. Karin Hannes runs the trans-disciplinary research group SoMeTHin'K in the Faculty of Social Sciences at KU Leuven, Belgium. She explores the potential of artistic, embodied and futuring approaches to develop and narrate activating stories that articulate the kind of city urban dwellers desire. With her innovative, co-creative research approaches she actively pushes for social change in society. Karin works from an activist, inclusive perspective. She contributes to an increased sense of belonging and connection between different agents populating particular neighborhoods. Karin chairs the European Network of Qualitative Inquiry and curates Townsquare13, a free space for lateral thinkers in her home town.

Welcome Plenary & Round table:

Countering Mistrust in Research and Science: The Role of Methods

Abstract: Abstract: Science, its institutions and its processes of producing knowledge are increasingly being called into question by research participants, potential research beneficiaries, the political sphere and the public more broadly. Reasons for this mistrust are diverse: From a lack of understanding of scientific processes, a general mistrust of elites, to personal experiences, having felt exploited, marginalized and mistreated by researchers, the inability of science to adequately cover and understand different experiences and perhaps acknowledge different ways of knowing, to the instrumentalization of science skepticism for political ends. Proposals to address these trends have included a call for increased transparency and replicability in scientific research, more participatory and inclusive research processes, the need to address racial and other biases in research, a redistribution of the resources and benefits that drive a global system of research production, and so on. In this roundtable diverse experts from different fields of social science and different methodological schools discuss the role the research methods (and ethics as an integral part of our methods toolsets) can, should and perhaps cannot play in addressing the mistrust, distrust and scepticism research and science are facing from their various constituencies.

Timothy C. Guetterman, PhD, is an applied research methodologist specialized in general research design and mixed methods research. Tim is an Associate Professor and Associate Director of the Mixed Methods Program at the University of Michigan. His methodological interest is to advance rigorous methods of quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods research, particularly strategies for intersecting and integrating qualitative and quantitative research. He also conducts NIH-funded health services research with a particular focus on improving health services using informatics technology. Tim also focuses on teaching, learning, and research methods capacity building. He has extensive professional experience conducting program evaluation with a focus on educational and healthcare programs. He co-authored the sixth and seventh editions of *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*, with John W. Creswell. He serves as Co-Editor in Chief for the *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*.

Emmanuel Remi Aiyede is a professor of political institutions, governance, and public policy in the department of political science at the University of Ibadan. He is the current head of the political science department (01 August 2020), former Sub-Dean of Faculty of the Social Sciences (2012-2014), and former coordinator of the Leadership and Governance Programme (2010-2014) at the Centre for Sustainable De-

York in 2000. He began his career as a fellow at the Governance Unit of the Development Policy Centre (DPC), an independent think tank in Ibadan in 1998, after a brief stint in journalism. He taught at the University of Lagos before joining the University of Ibadan in 2005. He has had visiting lectureship experience in several universities within and outside Africa. He has been on the Editorial Board of Nigeria's oldest surviving newspaper, the Nigerian Tribune, since 2008. He contributes to public discourse in the Nigerian news media.

mental issues. She also received training in science communication (Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society, Berlin University Alliance), and in open source intelligence to counter online misinformation (Atlantic Council, USA).

velopment at the University of Ibadan. He was also a visiting scholar at the Electoral Institute, Independent National Electoral Commission, Abuja (2016-2017) and visiting fellow of the Transregional Centre for Democratic Studies (TCDS) at New School University in New

Bruna Távora holds a PhD in Communication Studies and is a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Münster's Communication Institute, where she investigates the political economy of environmental misinformation, focusing on the links between the political uses of climate and science denialism, and the advancement of corporate interests over nature and land. As a research associate at the Getulio Vargas Foundation and at the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, she has co-authored several reports on misinformation in digital platforms, addressing issues such as epistemic crisis and the influence of digital media on public debate. Bruna has also worked with civil society organizations to strengthen science communication, where she developed narratives to promote community engagement with science on environ-

Event Structure

Tracks

- **AI Driven Methods:** Agent-based/multi-agent systems, zero-shot/few-shot transfer learning, reinforcement learning, online and continual learning, explainable and interpretable AI, edge AI, AI ethics, reproducibility and FAIRness in AI, generative AI, the application of AI driven methods in human sciences, etc.
- **New approaches in qualitative methods:** Feminist, indigenous and decolonial methodologies, creative and arts-based methods, practice as research, visual research, etc.
- **Towards a fairer research practice:** relational and care-centric methods, participatory, community-based and community-centric methods, research ethics and design, etc.
- **New ways to bridge/combine research methods:** emerging mixed-and-multimethod designs, bridging qualitative research and computer-intensive methods, connecting field research with online methods, connecting qualitative research with computational methods, exploiting both qualitative and quantitative data for SNA, incorporating reflexivity into quantitative-oriented research, etc.
- **Methods toolboxes for applied and policy-oriented research:** evaluation methods, bench marking methods, methods for prospective research and scenario-building/simulations, co-design and citizen science, participatory methods with stakeholders' involvement, etc. Teaching research methods: Pedagogical challenges and approaches, innovations in methods training, pedagogy of research ethics, etc.

Types of Sessions

- Regular panels
- Participatory sessions
- Training sessions, offered by experts/developers (both established and early career)
 - Short training sessions
 - Demonstration sessions
 - Methods labs
- 'Meet the expert' speed dating session
- MethodsNET Communities' networking & brainstorming session
- Book launch sessions
- Plenary sessions, including welcome plenary session, opening roundtable, 2 keynote lectures, and concluding plenary session

Program

Wednesday, September 10, 2025

08:00 - 09:30	Registration (continues)
08:30 - 10:00	Training session
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee break and networking
10:30 - 12:00	Training session
12:00 - 13:00	Lunch break
13:00 - 14:30	Welcome Plenary Round table: 'Countering Mistrust in Research and Science: The Role of Methods' Best Paper Awards
14:30 - 16:00	Panel with papers
16:00 - 16:30	Coffee break and networking
16:30 - 18:00	Keynote lecture 1
18:00 - 19:00	Drinks reception
19:00 - 21:00	Conference dinner

Thursday, September 11, 2025

08:30 - 10:00	Partners meeting Participatory session
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee break and networking
10:30 - 12:00	Keynote lecture 2
12:00 - 13:00	Lunch break
13:00 - 14:30	Panels and demos
14:30 - 16:00	MethodsNET communities brainstorming and networking
16:00 - 16:30	Coffee break and networking
16:30 - 18:00	Panels and demos
18:00 -	City tour with Benoît

Friday, September 12, 2025

08:30 - 10:00	Africa meeting Panel with papers Participatory sessions
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee break and networking
10:30 - 12:00	Panels & Methods Lab
12:00 - 13:00	Lunch break
13:00 - 14:30	Panels and Methods Lab
14:30 - 15:00	Coffee break and networking
15:00 - 16:30	Concluding plenary
16:30 - 17:00	Fringe events